

Real-Time Infrastructure Monitoring System Using Digital Twin and AI-Based Computer Vision Technique

Version 1

Description

The research project is non-economic in nature, as the scientific and technological knowledge generated will be disseminated in line with public information objectives. The research activities carried out within the project fall under the category of industrial research.

The evolution of digital twin technology, combined with IoT-based real-time monitoring, states a transformative approach to infrastructure management, especially in steel bridge. This study focuses on developing a real-time infrastructure monitoring system for existing steel bridges in Latvia. The aim is to detect structural changes in steel bridge, predict failures, and enable proactive maintenance through a continuous real-time AI-driven monitoring system. Sensors such as accelerometers, strain gauges, temperature probes and high-resolution cameras will be strategically installed to capture real-time data which will communicate through LoRaWAN to ensure minimal latency in data processing. A critical aspect of this study is the development of a digital twin, which serves as a dynamic, real-time virtual replica of the physical steel bridge in Latvia. This digital representation will be created using Building Information Modelling, integrating real-time sensor feeds for continuous monitoring. A dashboard will be developed to visualize the live status of the steel bridge behaviour, enabling engineers and decision-makers to monitor key parameters such as structural stress, environmental conditions, and potential anomalies etc. The system will be designed to provide automated alerts when abnormal conditions are detected, not only in real-time but foresee the future changes, allowing for immediate interference.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grant

Post-doctoral Research

Researchers

Muhammad Ali Musarat (0000-0003-0298-7796), Sandris Ručevskis
(0000-0002-0646-8064)

Organizations

Riga Technical University

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Real-Time Infrastructure Monitoring System Using Digital Twin and AI-Based Computer Vision Technique

Description:

The research project is non-economic in nature, as the scientific and technological knowledge generated will be disseminated in line with public information objectives. The research activities carried out within the project fall under the category of industrial research.

The evolution of digital twin technology, combined with IoT-based real-time monitoring, states a transformative approach to infrastructure management, especially in steel bridge. This study focuses on developing a real-time infrastructure monitoring system for existing steel bridges in Latvia. The aim is to detect structural changes in steel bridge, predict failures, and enable proactive maintenance through a continuous real-time AI-driven monitoring system. Sensors such as accelerometers, strain gauges, temperature probes and high-resolution cameras will be strategically installed to capture real-time data which will communicate through LoRaWAN to ensure minimal latency in data processing. A critical aspect of this study is the development of a digital twin, which serves as a dynamic, real-time virtual replica of the physical steel bridge in Latvia. This digital representation will be created using Building Information Modelling, integrating real-time sensor feeds for continuous monitoring. A dashboard will be developed to visualize the live status of the steel bridge behaviour, enabling engineers and decision-makers to monitor key parameters such as structural stress, environmental conditions, and potential anomalies etc. The system will be designed to provide automated alerts when abnormal conditions are detected, not only in real-time but foresee the future changes, allowing for immediate interference.

Researchers:

[Muhammad Ali Musarat \(0000-0003-0298-7796\)](#)

[Sandris Ručevskis \(0000-0002-0646-8064\)](#)

Organizations:

[Riga Technical University](#)

Contact: Musarat Muhammad Ali (muhammad-ali.musarat@rtu.lv), Ručevskis Sandris (Sandris.Rucevskis@rtu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvian Council of Science](#) | [LCS](#)

Grants: [Post-doctoral Research](#)

Project:

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

WP1: Digital Twin Development of a Steel Bridge

Task 1.1. Selection of Steel Bridge for developing the Digital Twin.

Developing a digital twin of a steel bridge requires the appropriate selection of the structure, which is accessible and in need of structural health monitoring. Field visits and interviews with experts and government officials will be conducted to get the on-field information.

Task 1.2. Collection of Blueprints and other relevant information to build a Digital Twin of Steel Bridge.

Upon selecting the right steel bridge that requires structural health monitoring, the collection of the relevant information will be made based on which the digital twin of the structure will be developed.

Task 1.3. Development of Digital Twin of a Steel Bridge.

Building Information Modelling will be utilized to construct the digital twin of the steel bridge.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose of data collection in WP1 is to gather all necessary information to construct an accurate digital twin of the selected steel bridge in Latvia, directly supporting the first project objective. The data originates from multiple sources including historical maintenance records, architectural blueprints, and bridge specifications obtained from government authorities, supplemented by field visits and expert interviews. Additionally, physical 3D scanning of the bridge using LiDAR or photogrammetry will generate geometric and geolocation data, which will be processed into a 3D BIM model using Autodesk Revit, serving as the structural and visual base for the digital twin.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Other

WP1 will involve both primary and secondary data. Primary data consists of raw 3D point cloud data captured directly from the bridge through LiDAR scanning or photogrammetry, along with field observation notes and interview records gathered during site visits. Secondary data includes existing architectural blueprints, historical maintenance records, and bridge specifications obtained from government authorities or infrastructure agencies, which have already undergone prior processing and documentation. The processed output of this work package is the BIM-based 3D digital twin model developed in Autodesk Revit, which itself becomes a structured secondary dataset serving as the foundational input for all subsequent work packages.

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- PDF
- CSV
- JSON
- JPG
- Others

The data collected in WP1 will exist in various formats depending on the source. 3D point cloud data from LiDAR or photogrammetry will be stored in open formats such as .LAS or .E57, which are widely accepted and non-proprietary standards for 3D scan data. The BIM model developed in Autodesk Revit will be exported and stored in IFC (Industry Foundation Classes) format, which is an open, internationally standardized format ensuring long-term readability and interoperability.

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

25

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

The existing architectural blueprints, historical maintenance records, and bridge specifications obtained from government authorities are being reused as secondary data in this project.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The data generated in WP1 may be useful to structural engineers, infrastructure management agencies, and government authorities responsible for bridge maintenance in Latvia. It could also benefit other researchers working in the fields of structural health monitoring, digital twin development, and civil engineering. Additionally, construction companies and smart technology providers involved in

infrastructure digitalization may find the dataset valuable for developing or validating similar monitoring systems for other bridges, roads, or civil structures.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

Yes

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Yes, a short embargo period of up to 6 months will be applied to some datasets, particularly the raw 3D point cloud data and the BIM model, to allow sufficient

time for publication of related scientific articles before the data is made publicly available.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

WP2: Optimization of the Real-time Data

Task 2.1. Installation of sensors on the steel bridge.

Task 2.2. Installation of VSS on the steel bridge.

Task 2.3. Integrating computer vision technique with VSS output.

Task 2.4. Integrating the sensors and VSS output with the built-in digital twin.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

[1 Data Summary](#)

[2 Research Data Management](#)

[3 Resources and Security](#)

WP3: Validation of the Developed Predictive Maintenance

Algorithms

Task 3.1. Development of a predictive maintenance algorithm

Based on the time series analysis, a predictive maintenance algorithm will be developed by incorporating all the output received from WP2.

Task 3.2. Validation of predictive maintenance algorithm

In order to validate the predictive maintenance algorithm, statistical validation techniques such as AIC will be deployed to observe the reliability and the one showing the most significant results will be selected to make the prediction for the defect identifications.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

[1 Data Summary](#)

[2 Research Data Management](#)

[3 Resources and Security](#)

WP4: Dissemination, Capacity Building, and Engagement

Task 4.1. Advertising relevant information on the project website.

Task 4.2. Publishing research findings in peer-reviewed journals, conference proceedings, and other relevant outlets.

Task 4.3. Organizing and participating in workshops, conferences, webinars, and other knowledge-sharing events to discuss project outputs and exchange experiences with other field experts.

Task 4.4. Connecting with industry partners to explore potential applications of the developed method and identify collaboration opportunities.

Task 4.5. Preparing a new project proposal in collaboration with mobility partners and other members to continue the research and extend the network.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

[1 Data Summary](#)

[2 Research Data Management](#)

[3 Resources and Security](#)

Powered by

